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THE VALUE OF INDUSTRY-ACADEMIC COLLABORATIONS IN SPORTSWEAR TO CREATE GAME CHANGING RE-USE OF TEXTILES.

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ABSTRACT

The context of this paper is the growing incentive for the sportswear industry to move increasingly towards sustainable design and production. Through a co-design case study, the authors look at the advantages of the sportswear industry and academia of collaborating in this area, with a particular focus on ways of generating value added garments through the re-use of textiles. The authors argue that with changing attitudes among the public the social and economic capital of re-use now makes it possible to sell re-use at a premium providing the garment designs are innovative and attractive.

Keywords: sportswear; sustainability; design collaboration.

INTRODUCTION

There are growing incentives for the sportswear industry to move increasingly towards sustainability. In terms of recycling, such an approach has historically been counter intuitive: re-use of materials has had the problem of typically driving up production costs (Van Hinte, 1997) while at the same time reducing the perceived garment value - and therefore price - to customers.

The authors argue that with changing attitudes among the public the social and economic capital of re-use now makes it possible to sell re-use at a premium providing the garment designs are innovative and attractive.

The paper discusses ways in which industry-academic collaborations can be better facilitated and how to encourage successful industry to embrace innovative new design thinking based on re-use (McDonough, 2002).

The paper considers the extent to which creative and lateral-thinking processes of students in higher education can facilitate “game changing” design thinking (Post, 1997) in collaboration with established manufacturers looking for innovation. Through examining a co-design case study, the researchers look at the advantages of the sportswear industry and academia of collaborating in this area, with a particular focus on ways of generating value added garments through the re-use of textiles.

The paper references “Fashion Technology: The Rip Curl Project” as the case study example. This was a project undertaken in 2009 by Rip Curl, the iconic Australian sportswear brand, with Fashion and Textile students at the University of Technology Sydney (UTS). The focus of this work was the re-use of old wetsuits and offcuts from new production neoprene to develop innovative fabrics of the same or greater value than the original garments. These formed the basis for jacket designs where the pattern cutting and aesthetic had to embrace the unconventional formats.

THE RE-USE OF TEXTILES

Waste defined as “unwanted or unusable material” (Oxford Dictionaries, 2011) prompts the question of unwanted or considered useless by whom? In the

sportswear industry, designers and manufacturers are increasingly realising the environmental, social and economic value of addressing waste in their products. However, for companies in the mainstream fashion and sportswear industries their conventional approach to design and business models will not always work in dealing with waste, textile waste in particular. Bradfield Moody notes that “Waste is the dead zone of profit. It can be seen as the ultimate transaction cost” (Bradfield Moody, 2010). New approaches are emerging both within the company and in external collaborations (O’Mahony, 2002).

In order to consider how collaboration between the sportswear industry and fashion education can offer new strategies for the re-use of textiles as a way of dealing with clothing and textile waste it is necessary to look at how waste is defined.

Caulfield of the Australian Technical Textile and Nonwoven Association, defines waste as “Any product or substance that has no further use or value for the person or organisation that owns it, and which is, or will be, discarded” (Caulfield, 2009). Caulfield goes on to argue that there is an environmental and economic value to much of what we discard. Sukhdev reinforces this point: “Pollution and waste, does it have to be a problem? No. You can make business out of recycling, out of tradable permits. There’s a lot of opportunity here.” (Sukhdev, 2010). Clothing and textile companies are increasingly recognizing this potential, with sportswear companies at the forefront.

Chouinard, the founder of an outdoor activity clothing industry called Patagonia, was inspired to use recycled materials in products because of his first-hand experience of pollution and climate change on the environment: “Can you have it all? The question haunted me as Patagonia evolved. Another problem would come to haunt me more - the deterioration of the natural world. I saw that deterioration first with my own eyes, when I returned to climb or surf or fish in places I knew, like Nepal, Africa or Polynesia, and saw what had happened in the few years since I’d last been there.” (Chouinard, 2005).

Caulfield describes the impact of sending clothes and textiles to landfill:

“The main method of waste disposal in Australia is landfill. Textile waste in landfill contributes to the formation of leachate as it decomposes, which has the potential to contaminate groundwater. Another product of decomposition in landfill is methane gas, which is a major cause of greenhouse gases, significantly contributing to global warming, although it can be utilized if collected. The decomposition of organic fibers and yarn such as wool produces large amounts of ammonia as well as methane. Ammonia is highly toxic in both terrestrial and aquatic environments, and can be toxic in gaseous form. Cellulose-based synthetics decay at a faster rate than chemical-based synthetics. Synthetic chemical fibers can prolong the adverse effects of both leachate and gas production due to the length of time it takes for them to decay. In the past textile waste has been incinerated in large quantities, emitting organic substances such as dioxins, heavy metals, acidic gases and dust particles, which are all potentially harmful to humans and the environment” (Caulfield, 2009).

COLLABORATION

The authors have identified examples of collaboration in which sportswear companies have engaged with new design and business practices in order to reduce waste and find new uses for textile waste at all levels of pre and post-production as well as post-consumer use. Several of these examples are discussed below in the following section.

Collaboration between sportswear manufacturers is of mutual benefit in terms of knowledge or production sharing. This can be seen in the forming of industry clusters defined as ‘geographic concentrations of interconnected companies and institutions in a particular field’ (Porter, 1998). Porter stresses their financial value: “Today’s economic map of the world is dominated by what I call *clusters*.” Silicon Valley for electronics and Seattle for aircraft are examples of how such groupings can be of mutual benefit. Clusters act as a draw for skilled employment, goods and services, encourage competition and help ensure the industry

does not stagnate as the status quo is challenged with the emergence of new start-ups. In sportswear, we see evidence of this clustering in the grouping of manufacturers of leading surf brands - Billabong, Rip Curl and Quiksilver - along a small stretch of the Great Ocean road highway in Torquay, Victoria state, Australia. The success of this cluster on the world market can be traced to "its early acknowledgment that its local knowledge, inter-organisational relationships, local supply chains, and retail successes could be translated to the world surf-gear market"(Stewart, 2008). While most of the production is now conducted off-shore, the business of innovation, design and gaining user feedback is still undertaken in Torquay.

The European Surf Industry Manufacturing Association (EuroSIMA) brings many of the leading surf labels together. Membership includes O'Neill Wetsuits, Billabong, Rip Curl and Quiksilver. One of their primary functions is to undertake research that is of mutual interest without divulging sensitive Intellectual Property to the competition. Many of their initiatives are focused on the environment. These include a neoprene recycling feasibility study and Ecoride, a policy where the objective is to reduce the environmental impact of board sports companies. In some instances the organization works with suppliers, such as neoprene manufacturers, while in others they work with event organisers to devise a more environmentally friendly approach to the organization of concerts and festivals.

There is evidence of the successful use of the cluster model within the supply chain model. NIKE is one example. Nike's 2009 Corporate Responsibility Report explains their vision of a future that '... will demand closed-loop business models that move closer to achieving zero waste by completely reusing, recycling or composting all materials.' (NIKE Inc, 2009). The company have developed a design software program titled Environmental Apparel Design Tool as part of its Considered Design Index. The software is designed to encourage greater collaboration between companies on the supply chain and with the design team. In their football jersey designs for the South Africa world cup in 2010 the company estimate that their use of

recycled polyester diverted thirteen million plastic bottles from landfill (Nike, 2011).

Patagonia's Common Threads initiative seeks to develop "a partnership between our customers and ourselves to make, buy and use clothes more sustainably, with the ultimate aim to close the loop on the product life cycle - to make old clothes into new and keep them from ever reaching the landfill" (Patagonia, 2011). The ethos is to reduce, repair, reuse and recycle. The initiative is an extension of Patagonia's original garment recycling programme and the company acknowledges the need for cooperation with customers and retailers to make this a success. An example of this is the company's footwear. Patagonia collects rubber flashing from the factory floor to reuse in recycled rubber outsoles. In their resoling programme they have entered into partnership with Mountain Soles (www.mtnsoles.com) to offer the repair service, advertising its availability to customers on their web site. In this as in other repair and recycling initiatives, Patagonia explains the process clearly for their customers. This makes the consumer far more likely to engage in the process than a label that simply says it can be repaired or recycled, but without guidance on how it can be done.

CASE STUDY: RIPCURL COLLABORATION

In this case study undertaken by the author O'Mahony we explore how new strategies for dealing with waste emerged through a collaboration between industry and academia.

The case study considers the approach taken by RipCurl to combat waste and goes on to appraise the collaborative project undertaken by the company and fashion and textile students at the University of Technology Sydney (UTS). New strategies for waste management form the focus of this study. The impact of the project on industry, education and general public will be examined.

The headquarters of RipCurl is located in Torquay, Australia, across the highway from the ocean. Employees are often surfers themselves. Like Patagonia and other sportswear industries, this involvement in the sport makes them very sensitive

to the impact that humans have on the environment. RipCurl's Curren notes that "As surfers, we feel first hand the immediate effects of pollution, we see rampant development on our coasts, we see the effects of a runaway lifestyle and disregard for the future of the eco system as a whole" (RipCurl, 2011).

RipCurl has undertaken a number of initiatives to improve their environmental impact. They are a member of CO2 Australia (CO2 Australia, 2011), the country's largest carbon offsetting company and provider of dedicated carbon sink plantings - managing over 16,500 hectares of plantings which equates to around 24 million trees. The motivation behind the development of their Green Wetsuit is described by Michael Ray, Global Wetsuit Chairman: "The laminating process has always been a particularly toxic one so this initiative of using non solvent based glues is going to be massive in terms of improving working conditions in the factories as well as reducing the amount of nasty pollutants in our air." (RipCurl Planet, 2011). They are also looking at ways of recycling and reducing waste using recycled PET bottles, polyester, wool and cotton to make yarns and through Project Resurrection, launched in 2007, recycling neoprene to make footwear outsoles.

The challenge for a sportswear company such as RipCurl is that waste reduction must be done in the context of being commercially viable. Hafkamp has identified four strategies for sustainable consumption that includes a shift from product to service-driven industries. These he argues are not merely viable but "...trends suggest that eco-efficiency can be enhanced by increasing the service/product ratio. This means that consumption can double, while the ecological impact is halved". (Van Hinte, 1997).

In 2006, RipCurl launched their own neoprene recycling project, Project Resurrection, which offers old wetsuits a second life as bean bag filler or soles for footwear. The problem with Project Resurrection is that it is focused on downcycling the material, ie: the material becomes lesser quality and is used in lower cost applications.

In contrast, the collaboration with fashion and textile students at UTS offered was an opportunity to upcycle the neoprene to create fashion garments that would offer the same or greater value than the original.

The original intention of this collaboration was to look at news strategies of upcycling old wetsuits. In upcycling, materials are used in a higher-value application than their original use.

However, after visiting the RipCurl headquarters it became apparent that production offcuts were causing a considerable waste issue so that Michael Ray, Rip Curl Wetsuit Product Chairman, asked if these be looked at. The reason for this waste is the 'cookie-cutter' approach to pattern cutting neoprene. The company believes that the method is necessary in order to maintain the high technical specification of their wetsuits. RipCurl estimate that their processes generated around 150 tons of waste each year.

The collaborative project took place over a six week period in 2009, with 60 year fashion and textile students given the challenge of looking for new ways of reusing old wetsuits as well as the fabric off-cuts from production. The project was divided into two stages. For the first, students were asked to design and make a series of samplers suitable for fashion. This was followed by the design and making of jackets using one or more of their sampler fabrics working on a design theme of the exoskeleton.

Students were presented with old wetsuits and these arrived complete with plastic and rubberized logos, pre-printed and waxed areas, stitching, bonding, zippers, and wear and tear. They were also given boxes of off-cuts in varying sizes, shapes, colours and densities. Technology and hand crafting processes were used in the form of knit, weave, print, beading, shibori, stitch, heat treatments, stapling, bonding and layering. Where traditional processes were used, it was in an unconventional way. Embroidery used yarns sourced from Reverse Garbage, a non-profit co-operative that collects and sells industrial offcuts and discards for creative and practical reuse. Chicken wire from a hardware store was used as the

basis for woven fabrics. In reusing the old wetsuits the challenge was how to utilise the existing logos and other surface details. In both instances a conventional design approach simply was not possible. Figure 1 shows some samples with the techniques that were used.

Figure 1. Neoprene textiles samples showing the use of textile and non-textile techniques by fashion and textile student Alice McConnell at UTS. Photo: Marie O'Mahony

For the second stage of the project the students designed and made jackets, designed around the theme of the exoskeleton. Highly sculptural forms found inspiration in crustaceans, insects and military armour. An example is shown in figure 2. The students were more used to working with fabric lengths or sheets of material, so the challenge of how to join smaller pieces of fabric became an integral part of the design process. Solutions included incorporating fastening systems from the wetsuits themselves, stitching, bonding and nuts and bolts. The success of the garments relied on the students employing a very high level of precision and rigor in their drape and pattern cutting.

The work was exhibited to coincide with Sydney's Rosemount Fashion Week in April 2009 showing a selection from the sixty jackets and about 200 fabric samplers. These were shown against a backdrop of a wall display made from fabric offcuts and a second showing a wetsuit cut along the seam lines and displayed flat to communicate the difference in pattern cutting for a wetsuit in comparison with a fashion garment. This is shown in figure 3. The exhibition allowed students and RipCurl an opportunity for interaction and discussion with

fashion designers, general public and media during fashion week.

Figure 2. Jacket design by student Anna Cahill showing influence of lace openwork to create a garment that can utilize small pieces of material making a feature of it. Photo: Marie O'Mahony

The feedback from RipCurl during and after the project was positive. RipCurl was pleased with the ideas and the new way of looking at neoprene and waste that it generated both within their own company and amongst students. The possibility of developing a research proposal for a Linkage or Researcher in Business grant application was discussed. This would have been aimed at bringing some of the ideas generated into production. Ultimately, it was decided that this was not the right time to pursue this in terms of economic and staff resourcing.

However, there were other benefits resulting from the project. The development of narrative was one of the strengths to emerge from the process. Although the wetsuit at RipCurl has a strong cultural,

technical and narrative history, in bringing it to students in the fashion arena the company felt that this was greatly expanded. The ability of technical and synthetic fabrics to age gracefully is something that designers struggle with. What developed in this collaboration was a strong sense of product aesthetic that is derived from manufacturing or production process. This is coupled with a sustainable fashion and craft language that although present in sportswear, is not generally highlighted in this way and brought to the fore.

Figure 3. Exhibition installation showing jacket by Su Choi and exploded view of RipCurl neoprene wetsuit in the background. Photo: Marie O'Mahony

DISCUSSION

Why might a sportswear manufacturer undertake to work with students rather than colleagues within the company or industry? The Young Designers in Industry programme ran in The Netherlands in the 1990s. This identified three key components - direct contact between industry and the recent graduate; a local (as opposed to global) character and the emphasis on ideas and visions that go beyond the daily activities of the participating companies (den Hartog, 1996). These three elements remain a successful formula to achieve value from the collaboration.

Direct contact between industry and students develops a greater understanding and mutual respect. For the education establishment it is an opportunity to engage with broader issues beyond the theory of sustainability and respond to these

issues and experiences in future courses and research activities. For industry, it is an opportunity to step outside the regular schedule and working practice. The enthusiasm and engagement is positive, although this can be raised artificially high. If expectations are not managed and monitored there can be a feeling of disappointment if the company or students carry the hope that ideas might be put into production immediately after the event. The balance between grounding the programme in reality and being truly innovative can be a difficult one to maintain.

The engagement with industry brings a fresh design eye to offer solutions that have gone unnoticed by the company. One of the key aspects to emerge from the RipCurl collaboration was a relationship that might develop further between high technology and craft skills.

Collaboration gives the sportswear company the opportunity to step outside their daily activities and design thinking. The creativity and expression in the education environment is unlike that of a company. Ideally, the experience is reciprocated and students are offered the chance to experience the reality of sportswear design and development. In designing a collaborative programme, it is important that all participants feel to have gained benefit in equal measure.

CONCLUSION

Sportswear companies are seeing the value of collaboration in order to reduce waste at industrial, pre and post-consumer level. Furthermore, collaboration is starting to feature within the companies with their supply chain, retailers and consumers. There is also much to be gained by the cluster model for collaboration within the industry sector, as well as in working with the consumer direct. The authors consider academic collaboration to be a valuable part of these shifts for the industry.

The collaboration between RipCurl and UTS demonstrates what can be achieved in terms of game changing re-use of textiles. For the company it has allowed them to explore a different area of fashion that the surf and street style of their seasonal ranges. It has also given them a much broader view

of new design and production methodologies. For students, it has given them an opportunity to utilise textile and fashion skills in an industry project. Students had to find a way of applying their knowledge of sustainability and new production methodology to their project in a meaningful way. It has been notable that since the project the number of students addressing sustainability in their subsequent collections has increased.

Finally, the authors conclude that there is short, medium and long-term value to be gained by industry-academic collaboration to develop innovative methods of reusing textiles in sportswear.

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